

Analysis of Factors Related to the Level of Patient Satisfaction in Hospital Care Services

Romliyadi

Lecturer in the Nursing Science Study Program
Bina Husada College of Health Sciences Palembang

Abstract:- Background: Satisfaction is of course what every human being always wants, patient satisfaction is an indicator of success in the quality of service provided and patient satisfaction is an asset with quality service will certainly get more customers. **Objective:** To know the analysis of factors related to the level of patient satisfaction in nursing services. **Methods:** This study used a cross-sectional design with purposive sampling and univariate and bivariate data analysis. The research period was April-May 2023. The sample in this study was inpatients totaling 85 respondents. **Results:** based on the five dimensions of satisfaction level found in responsiveness dimensions of 48.2% of the total 85 respondents, there is a relationship between age and satisfaction level p value = 0.000, gender has a significant relationship with satisfaction level p value = 0.000, education p value = 0.048 means that it is less than 0.05 indicating that there is a relationship between education and satisfaction level. **Suggestion:** always continue to provide the best service for customers/patients so that with the best service patients feel satisfaction, of course, they will feel satisfaction and can speed up the patient's healing process while being treated at the Hospital.

Keywords:- Satisfaction Level, Patient Nursing Services

I. INTRODUCTION

Patient satisfaction is the perception that expectations have been met, optimal results are achieved, health services pay attention to the abilities of patients and their families, pay attention to families, the physical environment, and respond to patient needs (Supranto, 2011)

Patient satisfaction is an indicator of the quality of services provided, and patient satisfaction is the selling power to attract more patients and patients feel loyal to come back, (Nursalam, 2018)

Nurses play a role in providing quality care when they interact with patients 24 hours a day. This is also due to the dominant number of nurses so that nursing services have a very strong effect on increasing patient satisfaction in the Hospital, (Nursalam, 2011).

Patient satisfaction with health services can be measured using the dimensions of the quality of WHO health services which consist of six dimensions, namely effective, efficient, accessible, patient-centered, fair, and safe, (Ministry of Health, 2016).

Factors that influence satisfaction according to (Muninjaya, 2011), namely: 1) responsiveness, namely the ability to provide services quickly, precisely, accurately and satisfactorily, 2) reliability, namely providing services quickly, precisely, accurately and satisfactorily, 3) empathy, namely full attention to patients, 4) physical evidence (tangible), including physical facilities, such as completeness of equipment, condition of facilities, alignment of facilities with the type of service as well as the appearance of nurses, 5) assurance, Nurse guarantees in the form of ability, safety and support felt by patients during treatment.

According to Anjarya's research (2017), patient satisfaction with services is indicated by a p -value of 0.019, while according to Tulumang (2019), satisfaction with reliability, responsiveness and empathy has a p -value = 0.000 ($p < 0.005$), Sinulingga (2010) satisfaction with the level of tertiary education is 57.5%.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title Analysis of factors related to the level of patient satisfaction in Hospital care services.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research design uses a quantitative method with a cross-sectional approach which aims to determine the relationship between independent and dependent variables using a purposive sampling technique.

The sample of this study were all inpatients with a total population of 568 respondents, then the sample was taken using the Slovin formula, totaling 85 sample respondents in this study.

The sample in this study was based on the researchers' reasoning with the criteria of inpatients, cooperative, early adulthood to the elderly with the research being conducted from April to May 2023.

➤ Research Ethics

Before conducting the research the researchers introduced themselves and the aims and objectives of the researchers then the patients were asked if they wanted to participate in this study, then they were given an informed consent sheet to sign as part of the research process. As well as the researcher conveys the confidentiality of data and does not disseminate it

➤ *Data Processing Procedures*

Information obtained from filling out the questionnaire was checked by means of: Edit checking the questionnaire obtained then checking again whether there were any questions that had not been filled in by the respondents or had all been completed, then calculating the number of respondents' answers was then grouped according to what was contained in the operational definition table, then Coding to simplify data management, namely changing the form of sentences or letters into numbers or numbers. The last is Cleaning. Data cleaning is to prevent errors that may occur when encoding data, incompleteness, and others, then corrected and corrected.

➤ *Data Analysis*

Data analysis used a computer with the SPSS program, then statistical tests used the Chi-Square test. The analysis of the research data is univariate and bivariate. In this study, univariate analysis was carried out for each variable and the results of the study, namely the independent/free variable (care service factor) and the dependent/dependent variable (patient satisfaction level), were analyzed using a frequency distribution table. In addition, a bivariate analysis was carried out to determine the correlation test between the

independent variables, namely nursing services, and the dependent variable, namely. Patient satisfaction level. A chi-square test with a significant level is used as this statistical test.

III. RESULTS

➤ *Univariate Analysis*

Test the statistical analysis of the frequency distribution regarding the analysis of factors related to the level of patient satisfaction with the independent variables of nursing services and the dependent level of patient satisfaction in services at the Hospital as follows:

- Frequency distribution based on the level of patient satisfaction in nursing services at the Hospital

The results of this study are seen from the dimensions of tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy then the level of satisfaction in service is grouped into three categories, namely unsatisfactory, satisfying and very satisfying. For more details described in the table as follows:

Table 1 Frequency distribution of respondents based on patient satisfaction level

Satisfaction	Frequency	%
Tangible Dimensions		
Less satisfactory	30	35,3%
Satisfying	40	47,0%
Very satisfactory	15	17,7%
Reliability Dimension		
Less satisfactory	27	31,8%
Satisfying	34	40,0%
Very satisfactory	24	28,2%
Responsiveness Dimension		
Less satisfactory	20	23,6%
Satisfying	24	28,2%
Very satisfactory	41	48,2%
Assurance Dimension		
Less satisfactory	28	32,9%
Satisfying	32	37,7%
Very satisfactory	25	29,4%
Empathy Dimension		
Less satisfactory	35	41,2%
Satisfying	43	50,6%
Very satisfactory	7	8,2 %

Based on Table 1, it can be interpreted from the five dimensions in the responsiveness dimension that 48.2% of the total 85 respondents stated that responsiveness in nursing services was very satisfying

- Variable factor analysis of the relationship between age and the level of patient satisfaction in the Hospital.

This study looked at the relationship between age and the level of satisfaction in nursing services. The explanation can be seen in the table as follows:

Table 2 Relationship between age and patient satisfaction in service

Age	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		P Value	OR
	Less satisfactory		Very satisfactory					
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Young	7	17,1%	34	82,9%	41	100%	0,000	0,000
Old	10	22,7%	34	77,3%	44	100%		
Amount	17	39,8%	68	160,2%	85	100%		

From table 2 it can be interpreted that the most age is 82.9% of the young age of a total of 85 respondents that it is very satisfying. Statistical test results obtained ρ value = 0.000 indicating that there is a significant relationship between age and patient satisfaction.

- The analysis variables related to gender and patient satisfaction in receiving nursing services at the hospital are as follows:

Table 3 Gender relationship with patient satisfaction

Gender	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		P Value	OR
	Less satisfactory		Very satisfactory					
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Man	8	18,2%	36	81,8%	44	100%	0,000	0,000
Woman	9	22,0%	32	78,0%	41	100%		
Amount	17	40,2%	68	159,8%	85	100%		

Based on Table 3, it can be explained that the most gender, 81.8%, was male out of a total of 85 respondents who were found to be very satisfied. Based on the results of statistical tests, the value of ρ value = 0.000 shows that there is a significant relationship between gender and the level of patient satisfaction

- Factor analysis of the relationship between education and patient satisfaction in receiving nursing services at the Hospital is as follows:

Table 4 The relationship between education and patient satisfaction

Education	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		P Value	OR
	Less satisfactory		Very satisfactory					
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Junior high school	6	24,0%	19	76,0%	25	100%	0,048	6,951
Senior High School	9	30,0%	21	70,0%	30	100%		
Bachelor	2	6,7%	28	93,3%	30	100%		
Amount	17	60,7%	68	239,3%	85	100%		

Based on table 4, it can be interpreted that 93.3% with a bachelor's degree obtained very satisfactory results from a total of 85 respondents, the results of the statistical test ρ value = 0.048 showed that there was a significant relationship between education and satisfaction levels.

IV. DISCUSSION

➤ *Frequency distribution of patient satisfaction levels in receiving nursing services at the Hospital*

Based on statistical analysis it can be interpreted from the five dimensions contained in the responsiveness dimension 48.2% of the total 85 respondents stated that responsiveness in nursing services was very satisfying.

The health service system is the most important part of improving health status by achieving this degree more effectively, efficiently and on target. The service system will be successful if there are supporting facilities, funds, reliable human resources, nutritionists, and other health teams. All

of these provide quality services that can provide satisfaction to patients (Mubarak, 2009).

This is in line with Rasmun's research (2019) where from the responsiveness dimension of a total of 67 respondents 90.2% said the response was fast in good service.

The results of the research, theory and research related to the researcher assume that quality services are of course accompanied by all supporting facilities referring to all service systems so that they can be felt by patients and can satisfy them so that the perception arises when nurses quickly provide services of course patients feel satisfaction.

➤ *The relationship between age and patient satisfaction in receiving services at the Hospital*

The results of the analysis are mostly young, 82.9% of a total of 85 respondents. Statistical tests obtained ρ value = 0.000 indicating that there is a significant relationship between age and patient satisfaction

Everyone will experience aging (aging) with physical and behavioral changes that everyone cannot avoid when they reach the age of developmental stage because this is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon, all of this will work depending on hereditary conditions, stressors, and a number of other factors (Stanley, 2006).

In line with Arifin's research (2019)), where out of 100 respondents 35% at a young age were dissatisfied with service facilities, with a statistical test result of p value 0.030. Shows a relationship between age and patient satisfaction. Meanwhile, this study is not in line with Oroh's research (2014) where 75.3% of the 100 respondents were old with a statistical test p-value of 0.539 meaning that there was no relationship between age and patient satisfaction. According to Rizal, out of 90 respondents, 52% were young, and the results of the statistical test, p-value 0.035, had a significant relationship. According to Aulia G (2022) where the most mature age of the 10 respondents is 54.3% of adults with a P-Value of 0.0201, according to Rasmun (2019) the age of 67 respondents is 82.9% aged with a p-Value of 1.000, which means that there is no relationship between old age and the level of satisfaction.

From the results of research and related theories and research, researchers assume that there is a relationship between age and patient satisfaction in nursing services.

➤ *The relationship between gender and patient satisfaction in nursing services at the Hospital*

Based on the analysis, it can be described that 81.8% were male out of a total of 85 respondents. The results of the statistical test of the value of p value = 0.000 indicate that there is a significant relationship between gender and the level of patient satisfaction.

Gender in the perspective of the education sector is that the illiteracy rate for women is higher, conditions like this mean that there is a difference between the sexes and this is not felt equally between men and women. One of the reasons is the assumption that women in education do not need to go to higher education, (Anwar, 2013)

In line with Oroh's research (2014) where 87.2% were male out of a total of 100 respondents. The result of the statistical test of p value is 0.005, there is a significant relationship between satisfaction and gender. While the results of Sihaloho's research (2017) out of 84 respondents were 50% female. Statistical test results p value 0.032 where there is a relationship between gender and satisfaction. According to Rasmun (2019) 84.6% of the sexes are female, satisfied with the service, the result is a p value of 0.525, which means there is no relationship between gender and satisfaction.

According to Rizal (2018) the gender of a total of 90 respondents was mostly 52% female. Statistical test P value 0.648 means that there is no relationship between satisfaction and gender. Meanwhile, according to Aulia G (2022) where the sex of the total 100 respondents was

mostly 73.2% male. With a p value of 0.028 there is a significant relationship.

Based on research, theory and related research, researchers argue that there is a significant relationship between gender and the level of satisfaction in receiving services. However, in this study, the male sex who was dominant felt satisfaction, this showed respect for the spontaneity of the male sex faster, even though the female sex was more sensitive because usually women put forward feelings. Therefore there is no difference between the two sexes in terms of receiving a service that is felt by each individual.

➤ *The relationship between education and patient satisfaction in receiving nursing services at the Hospital.*

The results of the analysis showed that 93.3% of the total 85 respondents had a bachelor's education, the results of the statistical test p value = 0.048 showed that there was a significant relationship between education and satisfaction levels.

Education is a learning process which means that the educational process occurs as a process of growth, development, or change toward a more mature, better, and more mature individual, group, and society. (Notoatmodjo 2003). Education is a change in behavior and behavior dynamically where changes in behavior are not only due to the transfer of theory, a set of procedures from one person to another, but these changes are due to awareness from within the person, (Mubarak, 2009)

This is not in line with Arifin's research (2019) that 49% of those with basic education were dissatisfied with a total of 100 respondents. The results of the statistical test p-value of 0.0001 means that there is a relationship between the level of education and satisfaction. Meanwhile, according to Sihaloho's research (2017), 85.7% of the total 84 respondents had an undergraduate education. Statistical test results p value 0.000 where there is a relationship between education and satisfaction.

According to Aulia G (2022), 92.3% of education has middle and lower education. With a statistical test, the p-value is 0.021. According to Rasmun (2021), 86.7% have low education with a total of 100 respondents. Statistical test results from P value 0.379 no significant relationship. Rizal (2018) 48% have low or lower education. With the results of the statistical test p-value of 0.795 there is no significant relationship.

Based on the results of the research, theory, and related research, the researcher assumes that there is a significant relationship between the level of education and patient satisfaction. This indicates that the higher the level of education, the more one feels and evaluates, and accepts every service provided so that it can cause a person to feel satisfied in assessing a nursing service.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions in this study discussing the analysis of factors related to the level of patient satisfaction in receiving services at the hospital are as follows:

- In the frequency distribution of patient satisfaction levels in the five dimensions found in the responsiveness dimension 48.3% of a total of 85 respondents stated that responsive officers in nursing services at the hospital were very satisfying.
- There is a relationship between age and patient satisfaction in receiving nursing services where $\rho=0.000$ ($\rho<0.05$).
- There is a relationship between gender and patient satisfaction in receiving nursing services at the hospital, namely $\rho=0.000$ ($\rho<0.05$).
- There is a relationship between education and patient satisfaction in receiving nursing services at the hospital marked by $\rho=0.048$ ($\rho<0.05$).

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